

The Data Springboard

Co-creating a Data Governance Framework for Strand-Aldwych

The Data Springboard is a concept developed between King's College London (King's) and Westminster City Council (WCC) to make better use of data for policy and communities. It emerged from the Strand Aldwych scheme and its Smart Working Group. This group explored the use of data to improve the newly created pedestrian zone at the Strand, and how sharing open, big and local data can encourage and promote cohesion and improve engagement with residents, local businesses, workers, and visitors.

Although this discovery arose in the context of the Strand Aldwych scheme, it has wider relevance to the local authority's ambition to drive transparency and innovation in the borough. The aspiration of the Data Springboard at its inception was to implement a data sharing platform, along a governance model and licence agreement. The platform should also include an established and tested set of data standards that will contribute to data interoperability between Local Authorities / Councils, the public, private and business sector. Such a platform would enable the different stakeholders to share data and insight for the common good, while safeguarding disadvantaged community members, and making the City more attractive and accessible.

WCC and King's have worked on the Springboard since 2021 and ran a series of stakeholder and engagement workshops in 2022 to establish community requirements. This document outlines our progress to date, findings from the co-creation workshops with stakeholders, and the possible next steps toward implementation of the Springboard, which should include the development of the governance, data and technical framework.

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ACTIVITIES

In 2022, three types of activities were implemented to inform the Data Springboard framework. All activities contributed a different perspective to the plans.

Across all workshops, our outreach activities reached a total of 138 individuals from 47 organisations, with 64 individuals from 32 institutions attending at least one of our events. The highest reach and attendance were within King's and WCC, but we also had strong representation from the London Data Store, SOLT, Somerset House and St Mary Le Strand Church. While we reached many Businesses and Universities, they all only engaged in a single event. Some stakeholders, such as The Courtauld, were unable to attend any events. Most of the people we engaged with were local to Strand Aldwych. We did find that several other London Boroughs (Hackney, Haringey) dipped into our events to learn about the project.

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DATA STEWARDSHIP LEGAL FRAMEWORK

Funded by the Connected Places Catapult, Gowling WLG conducted an extensive legal analysis of data sharing models, including case studies and a risk/benefit analysis. They identified three key categories of data sharing frameworks (Corporate, Contractual, Other), each suited to a different of use cases and with multiple options for implementation. They recommended the three options in the *Contractual* category as the most suitable option for the Data Springboard, because they would be flexible to adjust to changing needs of stakeholders, and neither requires pooling data, nor necessitate the incorporation of a new legal entity to hold it.

The three options in the *Contractual* category included:

Data exchange: a multi-party agreement that allows each signatory to share data with other signatories on the same set of terms. This would build trust as all sources and users are subject to

the same terms. Governance mechanisms could be built into the agreement to ensure that all signatories had to vote or agree before permitting new signatories to sign up to the agreement.

Data club: where a closed (i.e. limited) group of entities give all their data to one company within the group (likely to be a pre-existing company which is already known to, and trusted by, the sources), and the company holding the data runs analysis on the data or processes it in various ways, and then licenses back out the resulting analysis to that group.

Data marketplace: an intermediary operates a platform on which sources (sellers) can advertise datasets (products) and from which users (buyers) can come to identify data sets that are of interest. However, legally, marketplaces can operate very differently.

Another option of the *Other* category included:

Open access: where the data source chooses to make a data set publicly available under an 'open' license.

These four options were used in our subsequent activities (see below), with the goal to discuss and identify the most suitable framework for the diverse stakeholders of the Data Springboard.

In their final report, Gowling have added an additional option under the *Contractual* category, which as not explored in our work, but might be relevant for future exploration:

Commercial data vendor: an entity creates a repository made up of data sets from multiple third parties. That entity then either makes those data sets available to any other third parties under a commercial licensing agreement or the entity combines and analyses the data sets (possibly creating derived data) and licenses the combination, analysis, or derived data under a commercial licensing agreement.

DISCOVERY

The Discovery phase was funded through an internal grant by King's, and consisted of four stakeholder workshops, two each focusing on challenges the Springboard could and should address, and the legal and community model that should underpin it. Both workshops were run twice; the first in-person, the others online.

Stakeholders from the Smart Working Group and wider Strand-Aldwych community were invited to participate. A total of 85 stakeholders from 27 organisations were reached, 35 of which attended across all workshops, and 17 of which attended at least one iteration of both workshops.

At the workshops, stakeholders were presented with information and context for both data sharing in general and the Data Springboard idea, as well as related legal and ethical concerns. Interspersed with these presentations, stakeholders were invited to discuss their priorities and vision for the Data Springboard.

Stakeholders were invited to discuss their priorities and vision for the Data Springboard at our workshops.

The workshops addressed three key questions each:

Area Challenges

1. What challenges should the Data Springboard address, and what should it achieve overall?
2. Which data could or should be part of the Data Springboard?
3. What ethical challenges or barriers to data sharing have you identified?

Legal & Community

1. Which of the frameworks seems most appealing? Why?
2. What should the membership model for the Data Springboard be?
3. What should the community values for the Data Springboard be?

All workshops were recorded and transcribed to allow for analysis of the discussions. We will present the results of this analysis in the following sections.

DATA STORIES

The last part of project implemented in 2022, funded by UKRI, aimed to engage the public in three workshops, leaning on the work of the [Data Stories project](#). The three workshops focused

respectively on the Data Stories project and data visualisation; the Data Springboard; and artistic data engagement.

All workshops were widely advertised across stakeholder networks and social media. 62 interested stakeholders from at least 30 organisations were reached, 33 of which attended at least one event. Some participants attended multiple events. All workshops were held in-person, with the first two hosted by WCC, and the last one hosted at King's.

The second workshop, focused on the Springboard itself, and progress to date in the co-creation of the data governance framework. It enabled discussion with participants from outside the established stakeholder network, asking the same questions as the Discovery workshops (albeit abbreviated). Feedback from citizens was important for the project to be able to reflect on concerns those who might be affected or part of datasets might have regarding data sharing in a public environment.

The event was recorded, transcribed and analysed alongside the *Discovery* data, and is included in the below findings.

ANALYSIS

The transcripts from all events were analysed together through qualitative, thematic, inductive coding. This entailed several readings of the transcripts and categorising the different types of contributions. Through several iterations, the categories were refined and condensed into a core set. Alongside this, stakeholders were mapped to the categories, to identify the differing priorities of diverse target groups. A detailed overview of the stakeholders is provided below, and the thematic analysis codebook (containing all codes used in the final analysis, and their frequency of use) is available in Annex 2.

FINDINGS

In this section we will discuss the key findings from our analysis of the workshops, focusing on the key questions listed under *Activities/Discovery*.

STAKEHOLDERS & COMMUNITY

The Data Springboard community consists of five key groups, who each need and offer different things and have very different priorities.

- **Researchers:** This group needs access to data that is free, consistent, and reliable, with the ability to publish results of any analysis conducted. Researchers can also provide some data which might be of use for the wider community, and may be able to provide analysis for other stakeholders. The primary role of researchers would be that of data consumers, with secondary roles as data or service provider.
- **Businesses:** This group needs access to consistent data for their commercial decisions. They are willing to share data, but require a protected space to do so, as some of their data might be commercially sensitive. They also favour public facing elements, such as footfall (how busy is the area) and calendars (what events are happening). Businesses will only engage in data sharing if it is simple and at no or low cost. It is notable that the size of businesses will have strong influence on their ability to engage in data sharing, as well as the data they are interested in. Large organisations are both more likely to be able to contribute and make use of data, and be interested in more geographically extensive data, while smaller organisations might benefit significantly from both aggregated local data and service provisions. The primary role of businesses would be that of data providers and consumers, with a strong service element.
- **Government institutions:** This group has a strong interest in providing public services and information, and increase the use of data. They are likely to be mandated to publish data by law or following freedom of information requests. They are likely to have both resources and skill to publish data, and would use the Springboard to fulfil their public role. Due to these obligations, they favour open data models and do not require restrictions to data access. They are building capabilities to expand their use of data and enable their communities and partners to do the same. The primary role of government institutions would be that of data providers.
- **NGOs:** This group can provide data and wants to gain insight, but has neither skill nor

resources to conduct analysis in-house. They have an interest in making data available, and for that data to be used for public good. Their primary role is that of a data provider.

- **'The public':** This group required access to data summaries, accessible information, and data with a wider geographic spread than only Strand Aldwych. They are most likely to engage if they can understand what they see, and unlikely to require raw data. They will need tangible results to engage, and opportunities to feed back to the Springboard data owners. The primary role of this group is that of data consumers and – potentially – data subjects.

This group is both the largest and the most ambiguous. It was acknowledged as a stakeholder throughout the workshops, but impossible to define because the 'public' for a place like Strand Aldwych is extremely diverse. It includes tens of thousands of students, millions of visitors, residents, staff working in the area, or commuters travelling through it. All of these groups could be affected by data in the area being shared, but very few of them are likely to engage with the Springboard in a meaningful way. It has not been possible to get large scale engagement from citizens, primarily as engagement about a concept proved to be too abstract to garner much interest.

We identified five stakeholder groups with distinct goals and preferences regarding data sharing.

As outlined above, all groups have different goals regarding data sharing. Some institutions across these group have additional legal obligations, such as state-subsidised theatres having to fulfil obligations around environmental sustainability.

There was a general consensus among workshop participants that the Data Springboard should not focus on data only, but on enabling the community around that data and in the wider Strand Aldwych area. This should include facilitating engagement between data providers and users, understanding their respective needs and responding to them,

but also facilitating engagement between the various stakeholders, and offer a space for them to find common ground and collaborate amidst their different priorities. This could in turn be leveraged to enhance the overall experience of S/A visitors.

This community could be branded (e.g. "Strand Village") and used to attract more visitors. The community could also contribute different viewpoints on the data, and enhance the insights generated through these diverse views, thus increasing the value of the data for the whole community.

Participants discussed the role of the Data Springboard Community at length, including who is and who should be involved in the Strand Aldwych community as a whole. There is an active Data Springboard community consisting of the people and organisations involved in sharing and using data, governance discussions and decisions; and a passive community, consisting of tourists and staff working in the area, people who are part of the data and who may be targets of use of that data to enhance their experience.

The active community involves local stakeholders such as Northbank BID, academic communities (King's, LSE, The Courtauld), cultural institutions (Somerset House, The Courtauld), the creative industry (Somerset House Studios and Makerversity, Society of London Theatres), as well as external experts from the Connected Places Catapult, Open Data Institute, and Gowling WLG. The passive community is not yet clearly defined, and its shape will depend highly on what data is ultimately shared on the Springboard. The Springboard should engage these groups about what it does in different ways, and consider that different groups will have to be reached in different ways, and some (especially tourists) will be much harder to reach than others. Engagement can be interacting with the data, or simply being aware of that it is there and what is happening in the Springboard. Workshop participants suggested engagement methods including surveys, an open data portal, and public artworks. Physical or digital art *in* the space especially would provide citizens, who are unlikely to engage with the data of their own volition, and with an accessible route to engagement. This could interact with surveys and a data portal, as once they are aware, people may be able and willing to give feedback.

The potential role of BIDs for the Data Springboard was most discussed in the public engagement workshop. Participants suggested that hosting the Springboard might fit into the BIDs existing framework and align with their interest. However, while Northbank BID is an active stakeholder in the discussions and a strong potential partner for the Springboard, they have not voiced strong interest in taking on a leading role.

GOALS

Workshop participants discussed two different types of goals: Those for the Data Springboard as a whole, and those specific to what they want to achieve by using the data that is shared on the Data Springboard.

The overarching ambition for the Springboard is that it should benefit the entire community.

The core, overarching ambition for the Springboard is that it should benefit the entire community. It was pointed out that Strand Aldwych is public land, and the fact that it is not privately owned both enables the Data Springboard and the form of community envisioned by the stakeholders. The Springboard should decidedly serve the public and common good of the local community, and enhance the experience of visitors. It should also enable better and deeper communication and collaboration between the local businesses. Stakeholders also acknowledged that establishing the Springboard might hold benefits for democracy in a wider sense, by providing transparency, avoiding misinformation, and providing interested parties with reliable data sources. In that, the Springboard could help promote Strand-Aldwych as a green and sustainable area. Data on the Springboard should serve public and community interest. The Springboard should facilitate not just sharing data, but also sharing insight derived from that data. Some stakeholders may contribute insight instead of data, or in addition to it.

Stakeholders were united in their vision that there should be no plan to commercialise the data itself,

e.g. by using the Springboard to market datasets to third parties.

Proposed uses of the data fell into five broad areas, benefitting the different stakeholder groups along the needs defined above:

Government institutions could benefit from data to support policy decisions. Monitoring and continuous assessment of the area concerning factors like air pollution and traffic could help specify and track KPIs for the redevelopment.

Researchers and **NGOs** would benefit from use of the data for both the above policy purposes (by providing the analysis, or using it in campaigns), and any use of the data for studies on a wide variety of topics.

Businesses would benefit from using the data to enable forecasting of visitors and their needs, as well as benchmarking and comparisons, both within and beyond the Strand Aldwych area.

Visitors would benefit from the data being used to provide them with relevant information and narratives.

All stakeholders would benefit from increased efficiencies in the use of the space, as well as collaboration enabled by the data. One solution that was highly favoured was a shared event calendar for the entire area.

Stakeholders were united in their vision that there should be no plan to commercialise the data itself.

Specific proposed uses included:

For government

- Supporting policy decisions
- Predicting and preventing crime (e.g. pickpocketing)
- Evaluating area KPIs (e.g. cleanliness)
- Evidencing impact of area improvements (e.g. air quality)
- Benchmarking and comparing with other areas who share similar data
- Encouraging positive behaviour change in the space (e.g. cycling)
- Addressing environmental issues (e.g. air pollution causes)

- Live monitoring of the area (e.g. traffic)
- Creating a public data dashboard

For researchers / NGOs

- Debunking myths (e.g. necessity of cars for retail customers)
- Enabling research projects, including of the area as a whole (e.g. air pollution, energy consumption, spending...)

For businesses

- Forecasting visitor numbers and profiles (e.g. weather forecasts for outside spaces)
- Anticipating effects of planned events (e.g. Olympics)
- Benchmarking and comparisons to other businesses
- Mapping and directing visitor flow, and anticipating visitor needs
- Developing a loyalty app for the area
- Targeting visitors (if ethically feasible)

For visitors

- Providing relevant information to existing and prospective visitors (e.g. shared event calendar)
- Creating narratives about the area
- Enabling augmented reality experiences

Overarching

- Enabling efficiencies across buildings (e.g. energy consumption, CO2 emissions, loading bays) and progress monitoring
- Enable collaboration on events and schedules (e.g. shows, deliveries)

DATASETS

Stakeholders suggested a wide variety of datasets that could be shared, or would be useful if shared, which fall across the entire [data spectrum](#). In total, over 200 datasets were mentioned (including duplication), which we have summarised into six categories.

Public data: Stakeholders suggested the potential value of data about the public realm, such as traffic flows, locations of public toilets etc., as well as data that is already public but could be pulled together at one source in the Springboard, including bin and cleaning schedules. Some data, such as TfL timetables or weather forecasts, is

already openly available and could be brought into the Data Springboard to allow its contextualisation for the local community. Additional datasets are already shared for research purposes, including loading and access, traffic monitoring, 2D/3D models of the Strand Aldwych scheme, and weather data.

Business data: Stakeholders were very interested in footfall and sales data (e.g. tickets). Some of this data is already being shared for research purposes, including footfall and time-lapse footage. The BID also makes footfall data available to its members. However, more and wider sharing would enable more benefit especially for the hospitality sector. The Springboard could also be used to share business and other data that cannot be made public, but would enable the above-described benefits for businesses in the area. This could include contacts, audience demographics, or footfall data.

People data: Stakeholders were careful to not suggest sharing any personal data on the Springboard. However, tangential data, such as social media, local feedback, or mobile phone data (in anonymised form) was suggested frequently. Some of this data is already available to restricted circles and shared for research purposes, including Wi-Fi usage, and Hello Lamppost engagements. Stakeholders were also very interested in collecting data about Strand Aldwych from social media to understand their audiences better, as well as to create a shared event calendar that visitors could use to plan their visit.

Environmental data: The primary kind of data sought by stakeholders was air pollution, but data about green spaces, other forms of pollution and the wider physical environment (e.g. traffic) was also in high demand. Some of this data is already being shared for research purposes, including air and noise pollution data.

Research data: A small subset of stakeholders suggested the value of historical data for research, as well as new, diverse datasets collected through citizen science.

Security: A small subset of stakeholders was highly interested in security data. This included CCTV footage, information on active pickpockets or other crime in the area. Some of this is already

being shared through restricted networks. Including this data in the Springboard was perceived as too sensitive and risky.

Stakeholders suggested over 200 datasets that they would like to see shared.

Each of these types of data would come with different requirements if shared. Public data requires the least restrictions, as much of this data is already open; however, it will require additional services to be made useful, such as dashboards. Business data would require the possibility for confidentiality, and have a high requirement for platform security to avoid unauthorised access. Environmental and Research data requires potentially high volume and interoperability of the data, as well as measures to ensure data quality. People data – notably excluding explicit personal data – would need careful procedural review to avoid inclusion of data that should not be shared, as well as ethical assessments of the use of this data. It might require access restrictions. If there were longer-term plans to include Security data, this would require more extensive ethical assessment and legal consultations.

Sharing any of the above types of data will require definitions of a purpose for their use, which we will discuss in more detail in the *Implementation* section below.

BARRIERS

Workshop participants identified several barriers that could prevent stakeholders from engaging with the Data Springboard.

The primary barrier are resources, specifically cost and skills. Sharing data requires skills (to prepare data, bring it into the right format, anonymise it), and time to do that work; or alternatively, financial resources to outsource this work to experts, if skill is not available in-house.

There's a big gap between the small and large organisations expected to contribute to the Springboard, and the resources they have available to do so. Small businesses are unlikely to be able to be able to spend the resources to engage in the

first place, but also to get value out of the Springboard. To enable small businesses to engage, any process needs to be very easy and quick.

Participants acknowledged that not all data would be equally useful to all stakeholders, and that the data that can be shared on the Springboard is not necessarily sufficient to enable all the potential benefits discussed (e.g. hotels would benefit most from comparable data from competitors outside the area).

The primary barrier for stakeholders to engage in data sharing are resources, specifically cost and skills.

There are also technical barriers in terms of interoperability of the data and shared standards that make it harder (or impossible) for data to be shared in a specific format.

Another concern is competitors gaining access to data they can use against data providers, which would need to be included in discussions about *Terms of use*.

ETHICS & COMMUNITY VALUES

Ethics was inherent in many of the questions used to prompt discussions, and a consistent topic that workshop participants kept returning to unprompted as well. Overall, stakeholders agreed that the Springboard should be underpinned by the **shared values of inclusion, common and local benefit, and preventing harm**. Specifically, stakeholders highlighted concerns in six areas.

Privacy: There was extensive discussion of the use of personal data, and what risks data sharing could pose to privacy. Where personal data could be included in datasets, stakeholders agreed that the Springboard should ensure all data is should carefully anonymised, to limit risks of exposure, and meet the duty of care the stakeholders have. They were also keen to prevent triangulation of individuals from already anonymised datasets. There was a tendency among stakeholders to not share any personal data at all to circumvent the issue; but even if this approach is taken, triangulation still remains as a concern.

Safeguarding: The Springboard has a responsibility to ensure that the data it shares it not used to the

detriment of vulnerable populations. Two groups stakeholders were particularly concerned about were homeless persons in the area, or women travelling through the area at night-time. Stakeholders suggested there should be proactive steps taken to assess how these populations could be affected, and what could be done to prevent any use of the Springboard data for this purpose.

Inclusion: *Data being available* was distinctly not understood as synonymous with *everyone being able to interact with or use that data*. Different forms of inclusion were flagged as relevant, including language, platform accessibility, disabilities, digital and data skills, internet access, and smartphone availability. Inclusion for diverse people (citizens), as well as organisations (small businesses) interacting with the data was very important to stakeholders. A frequent suggestion to overcome inclusion limitations for citizens was physical *Engagement* in Strand Aldwych, in addition to any digital engagement. To engage stakeholders with limited digital skills or resources to engage, a suggestion that received broad support was to use the Springboard to provide also insight from the data, especially visualisations.

Transparency: Stakeholders agreed that the Springboard should make an effort to be very clear to anyone who could passively contribute data (e.g. by connecting to Strand Aldwych public Wi-Fi), to ensure they are – or can be – aware what data is collected and what it is used for. This should also consider language barriers (*Inclusion*), to ensure non-native visitors can also access and understand this information. One recurring suggestion was that, rather than only informing people of data collection and use, the Springboard could enable opt-in for data to be used for specific purposes, and engage passive data subjects in active decisions about data use: Asking “*What do you want this data to be used for?*” instead of explaining what has already been decided.

Bias: Stakeholders identified some data types as especially prone to biases. This included sentiment data, collected locally through physical feedback mechanisms such as smiley-buttons, because extremely positive and negative experiences would be more likely to get recorded; and data collected from social media, because only a very selective group of people uses such platforms to comment on locations such as Strand Aldwych. While stakeholders were in favour of collecting and

sharing such data, they were clear that neither of these datasets should be considered representative of the Strand Aldwych (visitor) population. In order to prevent biases in the data, or negative effects through use of potentially biased data, stakeholders suggested that the Springboard raise awareness of the issue, offer diverse data sources, and facilitate diverse data processors to work with the data.

The Springboard should be underpinned by the shared values of inclusion, common and local benefit, and preventing harm.

Data retention: Two types of data retention issues were flagged: Historical data, for which the use, consent, or other metadata was no longer available, and it is unclear whether the data can be shared; and more generally, how long data should remain available on the Springboard, and how it could be withdrawn, not just from the sharing platform, but any potential users. Stakeholders suggested there should be a mechanism to maintain the data lifecycle on the platform, including withdrawal and destruction of data. This was of particular concern for data that had already been shared with other stakeholders. Aside from data on the platform being shared ethically, there was also worry about how the Springboard can ensure and enforce that any onward use is also ethical. Responsibility for the use of data remains with the data owners, and stakeholders wanted reassurance that sharing data does not put them at risk. These points are discussed further under *Terms of use*.

Other ethical issues stakeholders saw included profiling, especially if the data were used by the police / Met, which might have repercussions for either individuals (e.g. facial recognition), or organisations (e.g. concerts in cultural venues perceived as 'risks' calling for intense policing).

The [Five Safes framework](#) was suggested to monitor and consistently address many of these concerns.

IMPLEMENTATION

Stakeholders had very different visions for what the Springboard should be and how it should function. This was to be expected, given the very diverse types of stakeholders involved. However, despite these differences (also outlined in *Stakeholders & community*), they agreed on some common themes and priorities for an implementation of the Springboard.

GOVERNANCE

Stakeholders saw the **leadership** of the Springboard best located with one of the organisations central to the process who enjoy their trust. WCC or King's were suggested as trustworthy for the community. The leader or owner of the Springboard would also be in charge of overseeing delivery and progress against community-defined KPIs, and collecting data to measure such progress. This in itself makes the leadership role resource-intensive.

Stakeholders identified two areas in which specific **oversight** would be required: Membership of the Data Springboard and members' contribution; and the adherence of members or third parties to the *Terms of use* under which the data is shared. If any rules were breached, there should be a process to escalate and rectify the situation, which the Springboard leader should be responsible for.

Stakeholders envisioned different routes to **engagement** with the Springboard. They favoured a membership model, where organisations could decide (and/or be approved) to become part of the community, and only members would get access to the data shared on the platform.

Small businesses were of special concern for the functioning of the Springboard. They would each only be able to contribute small amounts of data, but in aggregate their contributions could be very valuable for the whole community. However, they would also require a lot of enablement, both in terms of skills and resources to put data into the sharing environment, and in terms of decisions about the Springboard and how they can be involved in steering the communal decisions (as opposed to being outvoted or unrepresented).

What **resources** – data or otherwise – members can access, and what **contributions** they would need to make – data, financial or other resources – should be defined in the rules the community

agrees. These rules are in turn closely linked if not synonymous with to the legal model selected for the Springboard implementation.

Please note that the governance of the data sharing platform and the terms under which data is shared are treated as two separate – though closely intertwined – concerns in this report.

Governance refers only to the way the data sharing platform is overseen and implemented, and how the community is formed and makes decisions. The detailed requirements for how and with whom data can be shared is discussed in the Terms of Use section. The membership model implemented for the Springboard and the terms under which they may access data will overlap, but are separate decisions to be made.

The legal model of contractual data sharing governance is most suitable for the Data Springboard.

Openness: All stakeholders agreed that open data could be part of the solution, but it was favoured as a solution on its own by only a specific subset of stakeholders, namely those for whom publishing data is part of their mission statement. Stakeholders acknowledged that not all data, especially business data, could be made public without restrictions.

Figure 1: Hypothetical structure of a Data Exchange framework

LEGAL MODEL

Gowling’s framework of legal data sharing models included three main categories: corporate, contractual, and other. It quickly became clear that the contractual category held the most suitable candidate models for the Springboard, as they do not require incorporation of a new entity, and significantly less start-up costs. From the ‘other’ category, open data was also considered. We will now summarise the key considerations by stakeholders for their preferred legal models. An overview of the models considered, their key features and characteristics is available in Annex 2: Legal model matrix, developed by Gowling2.

Adaptability: Stakeholders were in favour of the idea that the data governance model for the Springboard could change over time, and that the first version of the Springboard would not have to remain the basic model for years to come. Indeed, growing the framework over time, starting with a small group and then expanding, was seen as a promising approach that maintained flexibility and learning along the way.

Data pooling: Some stakeholders were in favour of data being pooled, others embraced the benefits of decentralised sharing, which would not require them giving up control. There was no clear cut between stakeholders, but those with a public service agenda tended to be in favour of pooling

while those with commercial agendas tended to be in favour of closer control. The majority leaned towards not pooling.

Model: There was no one preferred legal model across stakeholders, which is in part due to the different expectations of the stakeholder groups. The most favoured models included the *data club*, where a central entity pools all the data and shares it out to others with restrictions and terms agreed by the community. The drawback of this model was that it required a central entity that would need to commit a large amount of work and resources.

The second favoured model was the *data exchange*, in which each data holder maintains their own data, and the community defines a core set of access licenses, which can then be used by others in the community without further requirements. This model was favoured because it was seen as least time consuming and fulfilling the low-maintenance requirement of many stakeholders.

FINANCIAL

Stakeholders agreed that members of the Data Springboard who contribute data or other resources – whatever form membership takes – should not have to pay to access shared datasets.

There was no assumption that the Springboard needs to earn money. However, there was discussion about how it would be financed, and how it could be self-sustaining. The dominating idea was some sort of membership models where stakeholders pay a fee for maintenance and data access, to cover running costs of the Springboard and ensure its sustainability. Alternatively, there could be a mandate for members to either contribute data or contribute other resources. This could include providing financial support, or providing services, such as data analysis.

Stakeholders who contribute to the Data Springboard should be able to use shared data for free.

The Springboard could potentially generate additional income – which could be used towards services, engagement and other commitments – by

offering access to data for non-members for a fee. This might require careful selection of datasets, as not all stakeholders might be willing to make their data available to such third parties.

There was a proposal to structure the Springboard membership similar to BIDs, where larger members pay the majority if not all of the cost, and smaller members (below a to be specified financial threshold) do not need to pay.

Aside from income, the cost savings that data sharing could generate should also be considered as part of the financial model. The membership model of the Springboard could further enable collective purchasing power and use of data towards the community goals.

TECHNICAL

Stakeholders had specific expectations about the technical functionality of the Springboard platform. The main requirements they raised during workshops included:

- **Simplicity:** The platform needs to be as simple and user-friendly as possible, to enable broad uptake, especially of stakeholders with limited skills and resources.
- **Security:** If data providers are to yield any control over their data, they need to be able to do so with confidence. Whatever platform is used must ensure that risks of unauthorised access are reduced as far as possible.
- **Verification:** The platform should include some kind of verification for users who want to access the data. An API should be available, aligned with terms of use for access.
- **User interaction:** Verifying users could also be used to enable outreach to existing users, and facilitate user feedback and stories. These would help to encourage future use and new community members to engage.
- **Beyond data:** The platform should have functionality to enable exchange between stakeholders. For example, users should be able to share and discuss insights derived from shared data. The platform could also offer additional services on top of the data, such as analysis, translations, or dashboards.

DATA

Stakeholders also raised a variety of expectations for the data capacity of the Springboard platform. These included:

- **Clarity:** Datasets need to be well curated and described, including appropriate metadata.
- **Quality:** Data quality assurance is required for all shared datasets, so that users of the data can rely on its accuracy. This should include some controls for inherent biases.
- **Variety:** The platform should be able to deal with different types of data, and not assume that all data will be static, or equally relevant to all stakeholders. Some data may be more useful in aggregate or processed forms than raw, or will require explanatory notes for context to make the data more useful.
- **Interoperability:** The Springboard framework should build on common data standards.

For sharing to happen in the broader community, it needs to be simple and user-friendly.

TERMS OF USE

There was no conclusive agreement on the preferred terms of use among stakeholders, which reflected the differences in preferences by stakeholder groups outlined above. The most commonly suggested terms of use for the data include:

Flexibility: Stakeholders voiced a general desire for access to be flexible. This could mean that datasets are listed, but not made accessible by default. Access levels could then vary depending on the type of dataset, the user seeking to access it, and the intended purpose of data use.

Access: Access could be defined either at organisational level (e.g. academic institutions can access this dataset, businesses cannot), or by scope of use (e.g. for research only, non-commercial use only). Access could also be granted to external stakeholders for a fee, which might be dependent on organisation type (e.g. fees for businesses, free for charities). Safeguards, especially around undesired forms of data use, would be required. Depending on the model adopted, external users could use a data directory

to pitch uses of the data to dataset owners, who could then decide whether they want to release it.

Openness: Several of the stakeholders - especially those with a public service agenda – were in favour of data simply being open. Some of them are mandated to make their data openly available anyway, and see the Springboard as a route to fulfil that public duty. The use of the data would increase if the model were more open, which might in turn benefit members. However, commercial stakeholders would not favour such a model, as a) it would create costs to open data that b) they would not be able to recover, while c) potentially putting commercially sensitive data at risk. A traffic light system to signify different access types (open, permission required, internal only) was strongly favoured.

Oversight: Stakeholders expressed a large interest in understanding who uses what data. Whether or not data contributes to public benefit and/or commercial activity was a key differentiator. While there was no perceived need to collect usage details from 'the public', data providers want to know who in the business or research area benefits from their data and what they use it for.

CONCLUSION

In this report, we have highlighted the main stakeholders of the Data Springboard, the commonalities and differences with their expectations for data sharing, and scenarios in which data sharing could benefit them.

The first and most important insight is that stakeholders want to develop not only a data sharing platform for Strand Aldwych, but form a community. This community could grow around the data, but expand beyond it. It would build and maintain trust between stakeholders, and form the foundation for continuous engagement.

Stakeholders were interested in opportunities for alignment between themselves, to enable cost savings and other economic benefits, and better understand and allow each other to respond to needs of both stakeholders and their audiences. They prioritised collaboration and mutual benefit – the Springboard should offer opportunities for all of them to contribute. One consequence of this is that the Springboard platform should not just allow the sharing of data, but of insights derived

from this data and further engagement with it, so that different stakeholders can contribute what is within their means. The Springboard needs to make it easy to share data in terms of technology and engagement, so that everyone is enabled to use it.

Stakeholders want to develop not only a data sharing platform for Strand Aldwych, but form a community.

NEXT STEPS

The next steps to move the project forward are to develop:

1. The data sharing governance model.
2. A proof of concept and MVP of the technical platform, including a data model.
3. Tangible resources to encourage engagement and feedback from stakeholders, including the public, and routes for interaction to facilitate both.

King's further plans a series of publications to disseminate the results of this work in different venues, such as The Conversation for an interested but non-expert audience, and an academic paper for specialist audiences.

DEFINING THE DATA GOVERNANCE MODEL

All of the specific data sharing preferences and framework models are heavily intertwined and interdependent, as Gowling's laid out in their prior report on the legal frameworks. It is unlikely that there *can* be a one-size-fits-all data governance framework that satisfies the diverse needs of all stakeholders. However, based on our work and analysis, the *data club* and *data exchange*, combined with an *open data* portal, would be the best route to implement the Data Springboard in practice. The open data portal should be used for those datasets that can be made public, and the wider framework facilitate all other data sharing.

The main drawback of the *data club* model is that it would require a central entity to host the data. WCC might be this entity, but would need to consider whether and what is possible to deliver alongside or on top of their existing plans. The

data exchange is the most adaptable and scalable, and allows for different data sharing terms and use cases for the different stakeholders. A core set of stakeholders could form the starting group and define the base set of sharing licenses for non-public data, which can later be expanded to include more stakeholders. A combination of the models, with WCC as a central entity, sharing data on behalf of, or facilitating sharing for other Springboard members, would also be possible – and our recommendation.

DEVELOPING THE TECHNICAL PLATFORM

The design and development of the technical platform will be highly dependent on the details of the governance model, including questions like where the data is hosted (with stakeholders or centrally), what data is shared (and therefore what security mechanisms are required), and who will have access (members, all stakeholders, or the public).

ENGAGING STAKEHOLDERS

Once the framework is defined, tangible resources engagement resources should be developed, such as a website, posters and flyers for local distribution, but also artworks based on the data, to engage with the public. A survey to understand citizens' perception of the plan, especially targeting transient and hard-to-reach groups like students and visitors, would be valuable input to further develop the framework and its underpinning values. This would also help determine how sharing of institutional, big and open data alongside resident perception data can induce institutional trustworthiness, encourage community engagement, economic recovery, community resilience and social cohesion and how this can inform policy change to benefit the area.

Whichever way the Springboard is implemented, it will be one of a kind. There are few examples to build on for this very specific, hyper-local, community-driven sharing approach.

RECOMMENDATIONS

COMMUNITY

1. Consider building and maintaining a community as a task in the wider Strand Aldwych scheme, as opposed to the Data Springboard, as this surpasses the context of digital and data. The Springboard may not be the right 'institution' to lead this effort, but should facilitate discussions and exploration in the wider community.
2. Develop user profiles and stories are developed for all stakeholder groups, including the public with its diverse roles. Initial users to consider include: Researchers, small businesses, large businesses, government institutions, NGOs, tourists, local staff, local visitors, residents, homeless, students, and external businesses. Both organisational and individual users should be considered: The institution King's College London will interact differently with the Data Springboard than a lecturer or student in its Geography department.
3. In defining the technical and governance framework of the Data Springboard, consider who the primary and secondary target groups are in terms of data provision and data consumption. This will have huge implications for both framework and technical requirements. a platform for government institutions and researchers to share data will look very different than a platform for businesses to share commercially sensitive data. Define membership types and/or licence terms reflecting the stakeholder needs.
4. Engage both the active and passive communities in the design of the governance framework and platform. Plan suitable feedback options for all stakeholders. Once plans have advanced and tangible results can be shared, communicate the Data Springboard platform and mission, data and lessons learned, to the public through specific *Engagement* activities. Create tangible and engaging material to facilitate this engagement. One option would be artworks based on the data. The role of the public should be re-evaluated after it has been engaged.

Whichever way the Springboard is implemented, it will be one of a kind.

5. If the Springboard platform expands beyond Strand Aldwych, consider whether and how smaller communities can be maintained and have a protected space for engagement. The strength of the Springboard as envisioned by stakeholders is its hyper-locality. While scaling up or extending the model to a wider geographic area would add benefit regarding data and resource availability, this hyper-local community benefit should not be overlooked.
6. Define terms of engagement aligned with stakeholders' envisaged data uses, rather than organisation types. The licenses anticipated in the Data Exchange model developed by King's and WCC, for business, research and culture use can be a starting point.

ETHICS

7. Apply good data practice and adhere to GDPR throughout. This requires knowledge of the status of each dataset, discarding any datasets with ambiguous provenance, setting time-limits for the use of datasets, and tracking who used datasets for which purposes to monitor for use of outdated data and potential abuse.
8. Futureproof the platform for legal compliance with current and incoming new legislation on privacy and AI especially. Use the [Five Saves framework](#) to ensure privacy where applicable.
9. Alongside the terms of use, develop a code of conduct to help alleviate concerns about abuse of the data and maintain trust for all concerned parties *including data subjects*.
10. Consider additional measures for how the Springboard can facilitate and maintain the trust that is required for successful data sharing.

IMPLEMENTATION

11. Some partners - especially WCC - are already working on technical implementations for data sharing, such as the air quality portal. Many of these plans will have made progress since our workshops. Consider whether and with which

of these plans that are already underway the Springboard could be combined.

12. Do not assume that the first model of the Springboard will be set in stone. Both the Springboard framework and platform need to be developed over time. Many potential users may want to see it unfold and understand the added value before they truly engage. The model should remain adaptable and flexible enough to change course, or even ownership, at a later stage. Whatever framework is implemented at the beginning should allow for such changes in the future, including provisions for such decisions by stakeholders.
13. Assume that the distinction between data providers and consumers is fluid, as people and institutions may move from one to the other over time, especially as they develop skills through interactions.
14. Consider facilitating data processing, e.g. by sub-agreements with small businesses and universities. This could include students working on specific pieces of analysis, or experts preparing the data for sharing and improving data quality and consistency.
15. Engage stakeholders, including citizens, throughout implementation, to ensure the platform serves their needs, and any issues can be addressed directly.
16. Map the already highlighted datasets to the model early, to assess how restrictive the access models need to be.

ANNEXES

1. Analysis codebook.
2. Legal model matrix developed by Gowling as used in workshops.

ANNEX 1: ANALYSIS CODEBOOK

Name	Description	Files	References
Barriers	What complicates engaging with the Springboard and data sharing for the stakeholders	10	28
Community	The different stakeholders of the Springboard and their (potential) roles, and how they might relate and engage with each other in the Springboard environment.	17	46
Data sets	Datasets that are, could or should be available to share on the Springboard.		
Business	Data from and about businesses (e.g. footfall, sales)	10	57
Environment	Data about the environment (e.g. air pollution, accessibility)	10	42
People	Data from or about people (e.g. mobile phones, social media)	12	39
Public	Data from or about the public realm (e.g. traffic)	13	37
Research	Data for or about research (e.g. citizen science, historical)	5	8
Security	Data relating to security (e.g. CCTV)	7	18
Engagement	Barriers and ways how the Springboard can engage with citizens.	11	24
Ethics	General ethical considerations in the implementation and maintenance of the Springboard (specifics in subcategories)	6	16
Bias	Potential biases in the data the Springboard shares, and ethical issues resulting from those biases.	4	11
Data retention	Duration for which data is held and tracking of consent across purposes.	4	6
Inclusion	Reasons why data may not be accessible / usable, different forms of inclusion issues, and what the Springboard should do to increase inclusive use of its' data.	13	23
Privacy	Adherence to GDPR, anonymisation, prevention of triangulation, not sharing personal data.	12	24
Safeguarding	Duty of care of the Springboard to ensure vulnerable groups are not harmed through the (use of) data	4	6
Transparency	Informing potential data subjects about data collection, sharing and use; offering routes to and soliciting feedback.	4	13
Finance	Economic factors to consider in the implementation and maintenance of the Springboard; whether and how it could or should generate income, how activities are funded, how it can help save costs.	10	13
Goals			
Data use	Goals for the use of the data; what the various stakeholders want to achieve by using it.	24	81
Springboard	Goals of the Springboard and data sharing itself; what the various stakeholders want to achieve by sharing data, and what they want the Springboard to contribute to the community as a whole.	15	26
Governance	How the Springboard should be governed, how decisions about the sharing initiative should be made.	14	25

Name	Description	Files	References
Implementation		5	6
Data	Data requirements of the Springboard; what does it need to be or look like, how to ensure data quality and avoid biases	14	42
Legal	Legal considerations and requirements for the Springboard implementation, including preferences for the different legal models.	12	31
Practical	Practical requirements of the Springboard; what is practically necessary for the initiative to go ahead.	6	15
Technical	Technical requirements for the Springboard; what technology does the initiative require to go ahead, and what constraints are there.	9	27
Terms of use	Considerations for access to the data shared on the Springboard: What data is available, who can access it, and what safeguards are put in place to prevent unauthorized access. How access is maintained in the long term. Licensing terms for data use.	13	4

ANNEX 2: LEGAL MODEL MATRIX, DEVELOPED BY GOWLING

	Features	Challenges	Sharing in closed group only?	Sharing in public interest only?	Governance flexibility (1 low – 5 high)	Limited liability?	Enables data pooling?	Issue if sources / users are competitors?	Existing trusting relationship required?	Requires outside funding?
Data Club	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Relatively fixed group of participants who all contribute and benefit 'Middle-man' acts as a repository for the data and licences all data in and out 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> May not scale 'Middle-man' takes a lot of risk in handling and storing all data (and bears costs of administering data) Better with pre-existing trusting relationship 	✓	✗	4	✓ <i>One organisation has to hold data for all members & incur liability</i>	✓	✓ <i>Could work, depending on party pooling the data & granularity of data shared</i>	✓	✗
Data Exchange	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Group of participants who all retain their own data No middle-man Data source contracts direct with data user All licence terms are the same for reciprocity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Each organisation has to overcome practical data sharing issues Creating a trusting relationship to encourage participation Who sets licence terms, controls participation, sets standards etc? 	✓ <i>Could be opened to anyone willing to enter licence terms</i>	✗	2	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗
Data Marketplace	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Any number of participants Marketplace operator could be just a facilitator, or could provide a service function or could contract with sources and users 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unless operator is just a facilitator, operator needs to be a legal entity Operator will incur costs it needs to recover 	✗ <i>Could put controls on participation</i>	✗	3	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓
Open Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data openly available, usually for no fee, to all. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The association cannot enter into contracts, so cannot control access which is legally enforceable. Has unlimited liability 	✗	✗	5	✗	✓ <i>(pooled data may become open)</i>	✗	✗	✗